

NOTES

Co-Ordination Chemistry of Quinquevalent Molybdenum-Oxothiocyanato Complexes

H. K. Saha, A. K. Banerjee and S. Mookherjea

It is known that ammonium thiocyanate and aqueous solution of oxopentachloromolybdate (V) yield colored, diamagnetic compounds of the type $R_4[Mo_2O_4(NCS)_6]$ or $R_4[Mo_2O_3(NCS)_3]$ (where R = pyridine, quinoline, trimethyl amine etc.) and such compounds with thiocyanic acid give $R_2[MoO(NCS)_6]^1$. Some physicochemical properties have recently been investigated by different workers but no systematic investigations have so far been attempted regarding these compounds.

In continuation of our work in oxochloro and oxobromo derivatives of quinquevalent molybdenum we have extended the similar line of investigations in oxothiocyanato series also. Starting from the non-electrolytic complexes red $MoOBr_3 \cdot bipy$ and yellowish red $MoOBr_3 \cdot phen$ (where $bipy = 2,2'$ -bipyridyl and $phen = 1,10$ -phenanthroline) we have isolated the black products of the composition $[Mo_2O_3(OH)(NCS)_3 L_2]$ (where L = $bipy$ or $phen$). We have also isolated the salt $Phen H_4[Mo_2O_4(NCS)_6]$ as red powder from $Phen H_2[MoOBr_5]$. In the case of $BipyH_2 MoOBr_5$ a gummy mass is obtained which is under investigations. These compounds have been characterised by chemical analysis, magnetic susceptibility measurement and oxidation state determination by modified ceric sulphate method. All these compounds are diamagnetic but the oxidation state of the metal is 5. In all probability these are oxobridged thiocyanato complexes of quinquevalent molybdenum as evidenced by diamagnetic character. The analytical data are given in the following table.

TABLE

Compounds	Colour	Mo(%)		CNS(%)		N(%)	
		Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
$Mo_2O_3(OH)(NCS)_3 bipy_2$	Black	26.21	25.89	23.30	23.48	13.10	13.22
$Mo_2O_3(OH)(NCS)_3 phen_2$	Black	24.39	24.24	22.25	21.99	11.90	12.38
$Phen_2 H_4 Mo_2 O_4 (NCS)_6$	Red	20.03	19.81	35.94	35.93	13.90	14.45

Detail investigations are in progress which will be published later on.

Inorganic Chemistry Laboratory,
Pure Chemistry Department,
University College of Science,
92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road,
Calcutta-9.

Received January 16, 1970